

Risk Return Relationship of Indian Textile Companies during Pre & Post Covid-19

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Abstract:

Background: One of the oldest and fastest-growing industries in the world is textile manufacturing. It's an essential and significant component of the Indian economy in terms of output, foreign exchange profits, and creating jobs. The global COVID-19 pandemic has impacted almost every nation on Earth. COVID-19 has not only seriously endangered human life but also seriously upset the social, political, administrative, religious, and economic order on a worldwide scale. The stock markets all around the world have crashed.

Methods: This research aims to investigate the risk-return relationship of Indian textile companies both during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The only source of data for this study is secondary data. Data has been gathered from the NSE websites to examine the risk and return relationship of Indian textile companies both during COVID-19 and after the COVID-19 pandemic. We have gathered the stock prices of Indian textile firms from 2018–19 to 2022–2023 (April–March). Then, to determine their true earnings, risk, and volatility, returns, standard deviation, and beta were taken into consideration.

Results: It was discovered that the companies' returns performed worse when compared to the benchmark index. The market index returns and the returns of individual equities showed varying degrees of weak to substantial association.

Conclusion: The pandemic affected the stock price positively and negatively for major stocks listed in the textile sector. This demonstrates that the impact of COVID-19 was felt by the Indian textile industry as well

Keywords: Covid 19, Risk, Return, Stock performance, Textile

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1. Introduction

The textile manufacturing industry is one of the oldest and fastest-growing industries in the world. The textile industry in India is the largest and most influential sector of the economy in terms of output, foreign exchange profits, and employment generated. Its relevance for social and economic cohesiveness is strengthened since it is dominated by a large number of small and medium-sized firms, which are often concentrated in certain regions and greatly contribute to their wealth and cultural legacy. This industry's propensity for non-random spatial concentration, with distinct patterns of productive specialization in some areas, is a crucial feature [12]. India's textile and apparel sector is thought to have significant export potential and generates a lot of jobs. It is a priority sector according to notifications from the Planning Commission, the National Manufacturing Competitiveness Council, and the NMP. The textile sector in India offers a suitable sample basis for comparing manufacturing productivity based on scale. It leads the industry for small-scale, or micro, small, and medium-sized, enterprises (MSME), as well as having an adequate number of large-scale businesses [2]. India has one of the most diversified textile industries in the world, ranging from the highly capital-intensive complex mills sector to the hand-

spun and hand-woven textiles sector. The knitting, hosiery, and distributed power loom sectors make up the majority of the textile business.

Dating back several centuries, the textile industry in India is one of the country's oldest sectors of the economy. Approximately 15% percent of India's overall exports come from the textile industry, making it one of the biggest contributors even today. It is among the biggest employers and labor-intensive as well. The hand-spun and hand-woven textile industries are at one extreme of the Indian textile industry's diversity spectrum, while the capital-intensive modern mills sector is at the other. The majority of the textile industry is made up of the decentralized power loom, hosiery, and knitting industries.

Remarkably, the Indian textile sector has undergone structural upheaval, constantly resurrecting and reinventing itself to cater to the demands of international consumers. Indian businesses have begun raising the standards and pursuing their HR strategies with vigor to enhance their brand and foster general growth. India is a global leader in yarn and fabric production, with consistently rising export quality goods. The Indian textile industry is highly innovative, self-sufficient, and autonomous.

The robust local and foreign demand is expected to support the growing Indian textile sector in the coming years. The retail industry has grown rapidly over the last ten years due to

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increased consumerism and disposable income. The entry of significant international corporations like Marks & Spencer, Guess, and Next into the Indian market has made this easier. It is estimated that the Indian apparel market will have expanded at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 11.8 percent, or 180 billion US dollars, by 2025.

1.1 Growth of the Textile Industry in India

Among the oldest and fastest-growing sectors in the world, the Indian textile industry is particularly significant to the country. The country became a sourcing hub with a competent workforce because of the easy access to raw materials including cotton, silk, wool, and jute. The Indian economy also heavily relies on the textile industry primarily reliant on producing and exporting textiles.

It accounts for about 14% of industrial production, 4% of GDP, 17% of export revenue, 18% of industrial sector employment, and 27% of the nation's total foreign exchange profits from textile exports. In India, the textile sector is the second-largest employer after that. 45 million people are directly employed by it, and millions more trained and unskilled workers can still find work in this business (IBEF, 2019). India is home to the world's largest textile and apparel industry, both domestically and internationally. The nation began exporting in the mid-1960s and is known for its beautiful workmanship [6]. Since then, the industry has helped the country achieve extraordinary socioeconomic growth during the past 40 years. At present, the industry is valued at US\$ 200 billion. Its contributions to India's industrial production in the country amount to 13%, its export revenues to 16%, its gross domestic product to 3%, and around 45 million direct jobs [7].

2. Literature Review

2.1 Effect of Covid 19 on Textile Industry

One of the oldest businesses in the Indian economy, the textile industry dates back several centuries. Even now, accounting for over 15% of all exports, the textile industry remains one of the biggest contributors to India's export earnings. The textile sector is one of the biggest employers and one that requires a lot of work [9]. As a result of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19), the World Health Organization (WHO) declared a worldwide emergency on January 30, 2020. On June 29, 2021, there were 180,817,269 lab-confirmed COVID-19 cases and over 3,923,238 deaths globally. Lockdowns, quarantines, and rigorous global containment efforts (government-imposed travel restrictions) could not reduce the incidence of COVID-19 cases [10]. The year 2020 began with the global COVID-19 epidemic, which has affected nearly every country. Along with posing a serious threat to human life, COVID-19 has severely disrupted global social, political, administrative, religious, and economic order. The cancellation of the biannual fashion week by the Design Council of India severely undermined the designers' promotional strategies. Retail sales stopped and malls across the country were forced to close as a result of the enforced social separation. The losses increased over time since the local businesses were ill-prepared to move their sales online [6].

The globe is facing challenges on all fronts due to the novel coronavirus, including economics, healthcare, politics, planning, and societal values in general. This has never happened before in human history. It is the worst nightmare of the policymakers, attempting to lessen its fatal effects on society and the economy while also seeking to slow its spread. The world was unprepared to handle a situation of that size when it happened. A lockdown appeared to be the only practical way to try and slow the virus's spread. On March 21, 2020, India also declared a nationwide lockdown, which is thought to be among the strictest lockdowns in the world [10]. COVID-19 has affected the economy of any country extensively [15]. The government of India has taken many corrective steps to meet this situation correctly and establish a balance between the demand and supply side for industries.

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, the textile and clothing sector had lower cash reserves and larger debt ratios than other sectors, making it more financially vulnerable. The entire financial market eventually felt the repercussions of the pandemic, and the textile and apparel industry in particular saw a sharp reduction in firm performance as investor confidence was lowered due to COVID-19 worries [1]. Nonetheless, the COVID-19 epidemic has hurt the textile industry's expansion. A large number of textile factories have closed. Owners of textile businesses have been forced to make tough decisions due to the crisis, including reducing salaries, terminating employees, and asking for unpaid leave [5]. The COVID-19 pandemic had a comprehensive impact on the fashion and textile industry in India. Kanupriya states that to comprehend the effects of a crisis, one must consider both the demand-side (social distance, consumer demand, and exports) and supply-side aspects (production, supply chain, employment, pricing of key raw materials, and imports). Regarding demand for the industry, consumer behavior during the crisis has significantly decreased. The nation's small- and mid-size clothing firms, as well as designers, are suffering as a result of closed retail locations. Throughout the world, the stock markets have collapsed [5]. Stock price collapse invariably resulted in significant losses for investors. Fears about the crisis and how it would affect the international economy quickly expanded to other parts of the world. Global markets saw similar falls following the U.S. market's worst-ever point declines, according to the China Daily report "Coronavirus: US stocks see worst fall since 1987" on March 17, 2020. That is, especially in situations like these, the U.S. market's performance served as a leading indication of the highs and lows of the world market [3].

3. Research Gap

Based on the previous studies, it can be inferred that numerous studies have been conducted about the effects of COVID-19 on the textile industries worldwide, including India. These investigations have focused on various elements such as supply and demand, supply chain tactics put in place during the pandemic, and more. However, to the best of our knowledge, no one examined the risk and return relationship of the Indian textile companies that are listed in NSE during COVID and post-COVID. Our research on the Risk and

Return connection of Indian textile enterprises was motivated by the findings of our analysis of the effects of COVID-19 on textile production, demand, and supply circumstances, as well as the effects on exports and imports.

3.1 Objectives of the study

- To study the Risk-Return relationship of Indian textile companies during pre and post covid
- To determine stock performance during COVID-19.

3.2 Scope of the study

One of India's oldest economic sectors, the textile industry dates back several centuries. India still receives a significant portion of its exports from the textile industry. It has a unique place in the nation. This is mostly because the country is a sourcing hub for raw commodities like cotton, silk, wool, and jute and has a trained labor force. In the Indian economy, it is also quite important. The year 2020 began with the global COVID-19 epidemic, which has affected nearly every country. Along with posing a serious threat to human life, COVID-19 has severely disrupted global social, political, administrative, religious, and economic order. Throughout the world, the stock markets have collapsed [5]. Considering the S&P 500 as a comparative benchmark, the study focuses on the risk-return relationship of these textile companies and determines market performance during and post-COVID period.

4. Research Design

4.1 Methodology

The only source of data used in the present study is secondary. Data has been gathered from the NSE websites to examine the risk and return relationship of Indian textile companies both before and after COVID-19. The stock prices of Indian textile companies from 2018-19 to 2022-23 (April-March) have been collected. The stock performance of these companies during the COVID-19 period has been determined. Then, Returns, Standard deviation, and Beta were considered to know their actual Earnings, Risk, and Volatility.

4.2 Evaluation Parameters

i. Standard Deviation:

A stock's overall risks are measured by its standard deviation. It indicates the degree to which the stock's return deviates from the returns of the benchmark.

ii. Beta

Regression analysis is used to compute beta, which measures how sensitively a security's returns respond to changes in the market. When a security's beta value is 1, it suggests that its price will follow market movements. If a security has a beta of less than one, it will be less volatile than the market. The price of the asset will be more volatile than the market if the beta is more than one.

5. Results and Discussions

This study focuses on data analysis and interpretation.

Specifically, the researcher calculated examined, and interpreted the data gathered from secondary sources through the websites of the S&P Indices, NSE Indices, and other websites. For the study, the researchers primarily took into account the following evaluation parameters:

- Returns.
- Beta.

5.1 Stock returns

In the present study, the authors have collected data from 192 Textile companies listed in the Sensex and randomly selected 147 companies for the risk and return analysis. The data have been collected for the recent five financial years from 2018-19 to 2022-23.

Table 1- Returns of the selected companies

Year	Above Median Value = (1.76112)	Below Median Value = (1.76112)
2018-19	147 (100%)	NIL
2019-20	128 (More than or equal to 6)	19
2020-21	NIL	147 (100%)
2021-22	NIL	147 (100%)
2022-23	147 (100%)	NIL

The benchmark S&P returns have been compared to the stock returns of each company. For analytical purposes, the benchmark index's median return was used, and in 2018–19, every company outperformed the benchmark index.

Even with the initial impact of COVID-19, 128 companies' returns have surpassed those of 2019–20. The textile industry was not significantly impacted by the COVID-19 outbreak since it was still in its early phases. The returns of these companies outperformed the benchmark index's performance.

During the years 2020–2021 and 2021–2022, these specific companies' performance was negatively impacted by the Covid-19 epidemic. These stocks have underperformed in the benchmark returns.

Over the year, the benchmark return for 2022–2023 changed. The textile sector rebounded after the COVID-19 epidemic, with every selected enterprise exceeding the standard.

Beta: A beta of more than one implies that the stock is more volatile in the risk analysis, while a beta of less than one indicates that the stock is less volatile. The author's analysis of the study revealed that every stock in the sample had a beta of less than 1.0, indicating lower market volatility.

Correlation: The stock returns of all companies are compared with the returns of the benchmark index (S&P)

Table 2 - Correlation between S&P BSE and Textile companies

Year	< 0.30 (Week)	0.30-0.70 (Moderate)	> 0.70 (Strong)
2018-19	39	84	24
2019-20	38	57	52
2020-21	53	82	12
2021-22	106	41	0
2022-23	59	76	12

According to the study, 57.14% (84/147) of the studied companies demonstrated a moderate level of performance in terms of returns in 2018–19, with 26.53% and 16.33% exhibiting weak and strong performance, respectively. The year 2019–20 saw a moderate–strong connection, with 38.77% (57/147) of the selected companies exhibiting a moderate correlation and 35.37% (52/147) demonstrating a strong correlation.

The correlation in 2020–21 varied from week to moderate. Of the 147 companies, 55.78% (82/147) demonstrated moderate correlation and 36.05% (53/147) showed weak correlation. This demonstrates the effect of COVID-19 on textile manufacturers.

72.10% (106/147) of the firms in 2021–2022 showed a weak correlation between the benchmark and the stocks. The weak correlation can be attributed to the COVID-19 epidemic, which impacted most industries, including the textile and apparel sectors. The industries worked to regain market share up until 2021–2022. The market began to gradually expand again in 2022–2023 and returned to the state where the correlation was between weak and moderate.

5.2 Stock Performance during Covid 19

Table 3 - 1st Covid wave Impact– 31/03/2020 March to 31/11/2020 November

Negative impact	Positive impact	No impact
ABFRL	ARVND	ABSC
ACML	AYMS	AKII
ARVINDFA	CENK	AMSP
BATA	DGJM	AXITA
BD	DOLLAR	BANSAL
BHIT	GNPL	BHX
BWSL	GTFL	BLB
CVC	ICNT	DCM
FLFL	KPR	DCMVL
GBGLOBAL	LBS	DMT
ICC	PAG	LUX
KTG	PRTM	RLXF
MUNI	TTAN	SREE
RW	VARH	ZE
SIYA		
SPAL		
TCNSBR		
VIP		
ZDC		

Note: All the stocks are Indian listed i.e. In Equity

The above-mentioned stocks for both 1st and 2nd wave pandemics are majorly impacted stocks, the highlighted stocks have too much volatility and have a major impact of COVID-19.

5.3 Analysis

The COVID-19 pandemic has impacted many stocks positively, and negatively, and for some stocks, there was no impact at all. The stocks listed in the above table had major implications. The stock of companies such as ABFRL, BATA, BD, FLFL, GBGLOBA, and RW were too volatile and fluctuating. These stocks' prices have been impacted negatively. The price of ABFRL fell from 247 Rs to 167 Rs within three months of the pandemic. In the same way, the price of BATA fell from 1650 to 1318 for just 3 months of the horizon of a pandemic. BD stock price fell from 94.45 to 61.19 Rs. FLFL price fell from 414.15 to 76.1 which has been decreased to the extent of 81.6% this Represents a huge negative impact on the FLFL. GBGLOBAL price fell from 774 to 514 Rs. RW stock price fell from 504 to 272 Rs. These are the stocks that have been impacted negatively. Stocks such as CENK have been positively impacted because of the pandemic, the price increased from 159 to 211 Rs within a 3 3-month horizon i.e. 32.7% increase. GNPL prices have been increased from 257 to 327 Rs. LBS price has been also impacted positively from 102 to 153 Rs during the pandemic period from March 2020 to May 2021. PAG price also indicated positive growth in share price from 22146 to 22746 Rs which is trading at a high price compared to other stocks in this particular sector. Even PRTM price has also increased within a horizon of 3 months during the pandemic from 32 to 84 Rs. These are the stocks that had a positive impact. Some stocks, like ABSC, AKII, AXITA, LUX, RLXF, SREE, ZE, etc had no impact.

Table 4 - 2nd Wave Impact

Negative impact	Positive Impact	No impact
DGJM	ABFRL	ALOK
GBGLOBAL	ACML	ASHM
GNPL	ARVINDFA	FLEXI
JAKHARIA	BATA	ITFL
LGHL	BHTI	JAIPURKU
PAG	CENK	MOCF
SELM	CVC	MUNI
STD	FZT	PASHCL
UPGL	DOLLAR	PDSL
VEKASL	GEXP	ZDC
VIFL	GTFL	
UREL	ICC	
VTEX	ICNT	
	KDDL	
	KEKL	
	LUX	
	RW	
	SPRT	
	VARH	

5.4 Analysis

The 2nd wave of COVID also had an impact on several stocks positively, and negatively, and for some stocks, there was no impact. Some stocks which had a negative impact in the 1st wave had a positive impact in the 2nd wave, and BATA which had a negative impact in the first wave, had a positive impact in the 2nd wave. BATA price increased from 1312 to 1619 Rs. GNPL had a positive impact in the first wave, and the aftermath of the first wave impacted positively GNPL share price, which increased from 400 to 524 Rs. SELM stock price had a huge negative impact there was a greater extent of decrease in the price from 2350 to 1350 Rs, a difference of 1000 Rs decreased within two months of the horizon. ACML's stock price decreased in the first wave, whereas in the second wave, its stock price started to increase, the stock was trading at Rs 527 at the end of the first wave, and aftermath of the second wave the stock was trading at 1571 Rs which is 198% of increase. CENK stock price continued with a positive increase even in the second wave. Even the stock price of CVC increased from 697 to 1937Rs within a month's time horizon. DOLLAR stock price has also increased from 135 to 311 Rs. LUX stock price also increased from 944 to 3105 Rs which represents a 228% increase. These were the major impacts on the stocks because of the pandemic effect. Some stocks such as ALOK, ASHM, FLEXI, ITFL, etc had no impact on the stock performances because the stock price fluctuated normally and stable.

6. Discussions

In the comparison of stock returns of the textile companies with the benchmark indices S&P we observe that before the Covid-19 epidemic, all the textile companies were fetching good returns compared to the benchmark index. It followed till the announcement of the countrywide lockdown in March 2020. (Median return of the benchmark was taken as base). Even with the initial impact of COVID-19, 128 companies' returns have surpassed those of 2019–20. The textile industry was not significantly impacted by the COVID-19 outbreak since it was still in its early phases. The returns of these

companies outperformed the benchmark index's performance. The COVID-19 pandemic had a detrimental effect on these particular companies' performance in 2020–2021 and 2021–2022. These stocks have not met the benchmark returns.

The author discovered that every one of the chosen equities had a beta of less than 1.0, indicating that the stocks were less volatile than the market. The year 2020–21 saw a range of correlations, from weak to moderate. In 2021–2022 showed a weak correlation between the benchmark and the stocks. The COVID-19 pandemic, which affected the majority of industries, including the textile and garment sectors, is responsible for the weak correlation. Up until 2021–2022, the industries tried to reclaim market share. In 2022–2023, the market started to progressively grow once more, reaching a state where the correlation was between weak and moderate. COVID-19 has severely disrupted global social, political, administrative, religious, and economic order. Throughout the world, the stock markets have collapsed [5]. All these findings show that the Indian Textile companies are also not an exception among the companies who experienced the downfall in the market.

7. Conclusion

Over the past 40 years, the sector has contributed significantly to the nation's remarkable socioeconomic growth. The year 2020 began with the global COVID-19 epidemic, which has affected nearly every country. There was a decline in the performance of the capital market throughout that period. The pandemic affected the stock price positively and negatively for major stocks listed in the textile sector. The current study discovered that the companies' returns, particularly in the years 2020–21 and 2021–22, performed worse when compared to the benchmark index. The correlation between the returns of the market index and individual stocks ranged from weak to moderate. In conclusion, this gives evidence that the Indian textile sectors were not an exception to the effect of Covid 19.

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